

POTENTIOMETRIC STUDIES IN OXIDATION REDUCTION REACTIONS. PART VI. IODOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF ORGANIC ACIDS.

BY BALWANT SINGH AND SOHAN SINGH.

Oxalic acid, tartaric acid, citric acid, malic acid and glycollic acid have been determined by the iodometric method. The liberated iodine was titrated potentiometrically against sodium thiosulphate solution at 10°, using a platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. E. M. F. was found to decrease steadily with the addition of standard sodium thiosulphate. At the equivalence point, there was a sharp fall in potential in each case.

When a solution of an acid is treated with iodide and iodate in excess, an equivalent quantity of iodine is liberated. The reaction may be represented by the equation

The iodine that is liberated can be titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate, thus affording a method for the determination of an acid. At higher hydrogen-ion concentrations the reaction proceeds practically instantaneously so that the method is well adapted to the determination of strong acids (Kolthoff, *Pharm. Weekbl.*, 1920, 57, 63).

In the case of moderately strong acids, like oxalic, tartaric and acetic, the theoretical amount of iodine is not liberated even after twenty-four hours' action with the iodate-iodide mixture (Groger, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1890, 3, 353). Weaker acids cannot be titrated directly by this iodometric method because the hydrogen-ion concentration becomes too small at the end to permit the reaction to proceed quantitatively.

Bruhns (*Z. anal. Chem.* 1916, 55, 45) has shown that oxalic acid may be titrated after the addition of calcium or magnesium salt. The oxalate ions are precipitated and an equivalent amount of a strong mineral acid is liberated. Kolthoff ("Volumetric Analysis", 1929, Vol. II, p. 390) has found that the anions of the organic hydroxy-acids form complex ions with calcium, barium, magnesium or zinc salts. The acidity of the solutions is thereby increased. The organic hydroxy-acids are, therefore, capable of quantitative determination by the iodometric method.

In the present investigation oxalic acid, tartaric acid, citric acid, malic acid and glycollic acid have been determined potentiometrically by the iodo-

metric method using barium, zinc or magnesium salt as the precipitating agent.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A known weight of the organic acid was dissolved in water. The solution was mixed with barium, zinc or magnesium salt and an excess of potassium iodide and potassium iodate. The liberated iodine was titrated potentiometrically against standard sodium thiosulphate at 10° using a platinum electrode coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The titrant was added from a burette and the mixture was kept stirred by a mechanical stirrer. A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. One titration as typical of that set, is recorded in the following table.

TABLE I.

Titration of 0.0337 g. of tartaric acid dissolved in 20 c.c. of water, mixed with 10 c.c. of 10% BaCl₂, 10 c.c. of M/10-KI and 10 c.c. of M/20-KIO₃ against M/50-Na₂S₂O₃.

Thio.	E. M. F.	<i>E/C</i> (m. volt/c.c.).	Thio.	E. M. F.	<i>E/C</i> (m. volt/c.c.).
0.000 c.c.	0.400 volts		22.350 c.c.	0.296 volts	
		2			640
5.000	0.350	2	22.375	0.280	2800
10.000	0.382	2	22.400	0.210	(maximum) 800
15.000	0.372	2	22.425	0.190	400
18.000	0.365	2	22.450	0.180	160
20.000	0.355	5	22.500	0.172	140
21.000	0.348	7	22.600	0.158	60
21.500	0.340	16	22.900	0.140	23
21.900	0.332	20	23.500	0.126	16
22.200	0.320	40	24.000	0.118	12
22.300	0.308	120	25.000	0.106	
		240			

DISCUSSION.

In these titrations, with the addition of standard sodium thiosulphate, the E. M. F. decreased steadily till the equivalence point. At the equivalence point there was a sharp fall in E. M. F. in each case. For the

addition of 0.05 c.c. of the titrant, the inflection potential was of the order of 80 to 108, 70 to 90, 70 to 84, 72 to 84 and 70 to 92 millivolts for oxalic acid, tartaric acid, citric acid, malic acid and glycollic acid respectively. after the equivalence point, there was again a fall in the E. M. F. which became steady on further addition of the reagent.

From the volume of sodium thiosulphate solution required in each titration, corresponding to the equivalence point, the amount of the substance was calculated. In the following table, the values obtained are compared with the amounts of the substance taken.

TABLE II.

Oxalic acid		Tartaric acid		Citric acid		Malic acid		Glycollic acid	
taken.	found.	taken.	found.	taken.	found.	taken.	found.	taken.	found.
0.1890 g.	0.1888 g	0.2251 g.	0.2246 g.	0.1921 g.	0.1917 g.	0.2011 g.	0.2013 g.	0.2282 g.	0.2278 g
0.1323	0.1322	0.1575	0.1571	0.1344	0.1342	0.1407	0.1408	0.1026	0.1023
0.0567	0.0567	0.0675	0.0674	0.0864	0.0861	0.0904	0.0906	0.0684	0.0683
0.0378	0.0378	0.0450	0.0448	0.0576	0.0575	0.0603	0.0603	0.0456	0.0454
0.0252	0.0252	0.0337	0.0336	0.0384	0.0383	0.0301	0.0302	0.0342	0.0341

These results show that oxalic acid, tartaric acid, citric acid, malic acid and glycollic acid can be potentiometrically determined by the iodometric method.

The authors are indebted to Khalsa College authorities for a research grant and providing facilities for the work.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
KHALSA COLLEGE, AMRITSAR.

Received June 13, 1939